

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE GROWTH ON THE SOCIOECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF COMMUNITIES

Abdullaeva Madina Kamilovna

Associate Professor of the Department of Economic Theory,
Doctor of Economics, Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract. The development of social infrastructure in the world serves to increase the well-being of the population, for this the state is responsible for solving urgent tasks. In the era of rapid urbanization in the world, along with the development of infrastructure, the issue of improving the livelihood of rural people is among the highest goals.

Keywords: infrastructure, population, standart, method, economics, technology.

INTRODUCTION

Expansion of infrastructure service types and advancement of social infrastructure as a component of state social policy prioritize the formulation and implementation of innovative management strategies aimed at enhancing both economic and social efficiency. Particular emphasis is placed on improving systems for training qualified personnel, with a focus on quality education, healthcare, and the provision of household services.

According to international organizations, approximately one-third of the state budget in many developed countries is allocated to the development of social sectors. Leading nations in social infrastructure management, targeted developmental strategies, and implementation include the United States, Japan, South Korea, China, and European countries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In solving global economic problems, it is important to organize and improve the organizational and management structure of social infrastructure on an innovative basis. In particular, in the state social policy, systematic reforms are being carried out on the development of mechanisms for the effective solution of the problems of the rural population in terms of educational policy, housing provision, household services and health care. In particular, on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the

Republic of Uzbekistan dated 30.12.2022 No. PQ-465 "On Measures for the Development of the Social and Production Infrastructure of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023-2025" and further development of the production infrastructure, as well as the implementation of target tasks for raising the standard of living of the population and creating a favorable investment environment for entrepreneurs [1].

Social infrastructures and issues of improving the welfare of the population through their development are discussed in the research works of foreign scientists such as Y. Schumpeter, D. Norton, P. Drucker, P. Dowling, M. Porter, A. Raizberg, R. Kaplan, scientists from the CIS countries A.I. Gavrilov, N.N. Nekrasov, A.G. Sinelnikov, J.T. Toshchenko, T.N. Arbuzova, S.G. Vazhenin, A.G. Granberg, A.D. Eremenko. A number of Uzbek economists S.Gulyamov, N.Yoldoshev, B.Goyibnazarov, A.Rasulov, Sh.Shodmonov, Sh.Zaynutdinov, A.Sharipov, S.Khamraeva, Sh.Yuldasheva have conducted research on the theoretical and practical aspects of social infrastructure development [2, 3, 4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Uzbekistan will further increase the well-being of our people, transform economic sectors and rapidly develop entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensure human rights and interests, and an active civil society" the priority directions of reforms aimed at formation were determined". Raising the standard of living of the population and social protection of the population in the country was defined as one of the main functions of the state. One of the main objectives of the social policy implemented in our country is to ensure a high standard of living of the population. The development of social infrastructure in the country, the quantity and quality of services provided by the state, the level of development of the social sphere and the social protection system of the population serve as the main factors in improving the indicators of the standard of living of the population recommended by the United Nations (UN). Economic development of society is a wide-scale process that encompasses the concepts of economic growth, improvement of structural changes in the economy, improvement of living conditions and quality of life of the population. According to the UN Development Program, "the ability to use the resources necessary for living a long and healthy life, getting education, acquiring knowledge and living a decent life is the main essence of human development" [5].

The creation of infrastructure is inextricably linked with material production, and its development creates new types of production and activities in serviced and

integrated sectors. The growth of social labor productivity in the field of social production frees up a large amount of resources in society to provide services to the population. The creation of infrastructure means the development of production forces in the society, as a result of which the internal economic commonality of the sectors within it is determined by the fulfillment of certain tasks.

The structure of social infrastructure consists of:

- Housing and communal economy;
- Health maintenance;
- Education (education and training, retraining and upgrading of professional personnel)
- Communications and information services;
- Household service;
- Social support of the population;
- Science and culture;
- Public organizations;
- Sports, wellness and recreation facilities;
- Transportation of people (passenger transport);
- Preservation and defense of public order;
- Social security, etc.

Social infrastructure includes social-household and social-spiritual infrastructures. Improving the mechanism of social infrastructure development especially for the rural population is one of the tasks that the social policy of our country should solve. In the process of carrying out their activities, social infrastructure objects include the provision of services as well as the production of goods. In this, the goals of improving the standard of living of the population and reproducing the labor force are put forward.

In order to assess the level of development of social infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account the main tasks of social policy aimed at improving the quality of life of the population, increasing its well-being and longevity, forming and restoring a healthy, creatively active generation. In particular, achieving positive results such as providing the population with quality housing, increasing the level and quality of social infrastructure development, creating a cultural sphere of human life, improving the environmental conditions of life and work,

increasing labor productivity, creating guarantees of social protection for young people and pensioners is a systematic assessment of this field.

The activities of health care, education, housing and communal economy, beautification, employment and many other service entities aimed at improving the living standards of the population are embodied in the structure of the regional social infrastructure under investigation. All of them are primarily reflected in the legal and regulatory documents issued by the government of our country, mainly in strategies.

Social policy is a policy that reflects the priority aspects of state policy in the fields of education, culture, health care, pension provision, housing and communal economy, physical education and sports, household and social protection, guaranteeing the totality of all conditions of human life activity, material and spiritual benefits.

The activity that does not allow ensuring the well-being of the population is precisely the diversity of social infrastructure and quality services in the regions. As rural residents have the right to use quality social infrastructure services, the equality of reforms is a primary issue for them.

CONCLUSION

In short, the focus of the state social policy on human capital is of great importance in the country's economy. Through the social policy aimed at the development of human capital, the quality of life of the population in the country will increase and the standard of living will be improved. In today's environment, where education is valued as the most unique capital, at all stages of education, by introducing a mechanism for improving the effectiveness of the evaluation of educational results and the methods of financing the system, an opportunity will be created for all people to receive quality education throughout their lives. Medical services include services aimed at reducing the risk of disease, promoting and supporting a healthy lifestyle, and improving the health of the environment. Medical services provided to some individuals (combating infectious, social diseases) reduce the risk of disease of others. Considering the great social importance of these services, the state undertakes to finance the health care system in the country.

In our opinion, two different approaches to the estimation of the standard of living and the quality of life of the population are appropriate. The system of evaluation indicators is implemented with the help of social indicators. The national system of evaluation indicators has its own characteristics, these indicators are based on

methodological recommendations of the UN. The index of standard of living and quality of life is calculated on the basis of separate indicators. This approach is widely used by the UN and other international organizations to compare the standard of living and quality of life of the population in different countries.

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